

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SHAKALELA****FIRST NAME: ELIZE****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US XUK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 7

INTRODUCTION TO ACCADEMIC ESSAY WRITING SKILLS

1) INTRODUCTION

The ACA-401D coursepack for period one (1) focuses on the basis of essay writing, it informs me of pertinent principles and rule of thumbs that my academic writing must adhere to especially when embarking on writing a good thesis. Chapter one (1) of the ACA-401 coursepack starts off by highlighting the basics of essay writing. The chapter takes me through on a journey of what I should do and what I should avoid in order to produce a good essay (EUCLID 2019, 1). Especially the principle of allocating enough writing time and avoiding procrastination. These are essential principles that I will have to abide to both when writing my response papers (RP), major paper and thesis. I must admit that it is my first time to undertake an online course, I have always attended traditional face to face schooling and learning. It was my LLM studies, that made me realise that I didn't need a classroom to complete any studies and that is why I made a decision to peruse studies at Euclid University. I must confess that studying remotely is indeed really a challenge that requires absolute commitment. This is so because perusing both an LLM and a Ph.D. requires one to produce a thesis. Producing a good thesis is a daunting task that requires the student to invest a lot of reading and writing time. It requires the student to be a self-starter and a self-motivator.

Unit one (1) of the ACA-401D coursepack also, reminded me that a good academic essay, must always answer a question or a task and contain a thesis statement. Simply explained, a thesis statement is the answer to the question your thesis intends to investigate and includes the authors argument all at once (ibid.). I have also learned that in order to produce a good thesis statement, it is important that the thesis statement represents both the problem that the author has identified as well as how the author will address the

problem. A good thesis statement must be able to guide the reader of the author's position on the topic researched /to be researched and how the author intends to construct their argument on the said topic. I like how the Harvard college centre explains the thesis statement in a metaphor of a reader as a member of a jury, listening to a lawyer presenting their opening arguments.

The jury member will know very soon whether the lawyer believes the accused to be guilty or not guilty, and how the lawyer plans to convince the jury. Readers of academic essays are like jury members, before they have read too far, they want to know what the essay argues as well as how the writer plans to make the argument. After reading your thesis statement, the reader should think, this essay is going to try to convince me of something. I'm not convinced yet, but I'm interested to see how I might be. (<https://writingcenter.fas.harvard.edu/pages/developing-thesis>).

Therefore, it is imperative that before I start writing my thesis, I think of the topic that I want to write about. Thereafter, I must formulate questions that my thesis wishes to investigate. And then once I have this information, I must then be able to formulate a good thesis statement which will guide my reader of my topic, about my opinion on the topic and my arguments on the subject matter.

2) PLAGARISM

Chapter two (2), Unit one (1) of the coursepack unpacks the term plagiarism and the forms it takes. This chapter also reminds me that plagiarism is a serious academic offence and that I should guard against it at all costs. The chapter further defines plagiarism as an act committed when a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of the source of information (EUCLID 2019, 5). Therefore, if I use someone else's words or ideas without citing the author(s) I commit an act of plagiarism. Chapter two (2) of unit one (1) also reminds me that I will also commit plagiarism if I ask someone else to write my response papers on my behalf while attesting that it is my work by putting my name on the RP. And submitting it to my professor for assessment purposes (ibid.). The chapter teaches me of ways that I should implore as a student in order avoid the act of plagiarism. Some of the ways to avoid plagiarism is simply by acknowledging that certain material is borrowed and providing the audience with necessary information to find the source from where the source is borrowed from (<http://www.hunter.cuny.edu/studentaffairs/repository/files/What%20is%20Plagiarism.pdf/view?searchterm=>).

a) Source not cited

One of the preferred academic ways to avoid plagiarism is to properly cite the author or source that has provided the information that an author is using (EUCLID 2019, 6). Citing can either be in –text citation and or by list of work cited. Therefore, when I write my RP papers or my major papers, especially if I use someone else's idea or words without acknowledging their work by either citation or by list of references I will be considered to

have plagiarised. Chapter two (2), unit one (1) course pack reminds me to ensure that I guard from paraphrasing from other sources instead of spending time reading, researching and that I should put more effort on original work <http://www.hunter.cuny.edu/studentaffairs/repository/files/What%20is%20Plagiarism.pdf/view?searchterm=>.

b) Source cited but still plagiarism

For myself, when I read about this form of plagiarism, of an author who cites the source and may still be considered as plagiarism I was a bit confused. For example, it will be considered as plagiarism if I provide false information regarding where I obtained certain information, in other words when I cite an inaccurate or unexciting source. This will make it impossible for my instructor to find the source because the source is wrong. (<http://www.hunter.cuny.edu/studentaffairs/repository/files/What%20is%20Plagiarism.pdf>).

Furthermore, chapter two (2) of the EUCLID coursepack also teaches me when not to cite while also providing me with examples of instances that I can draw from on when it will be considered as plagiarism. For example, when the information I am writing is common knowledge, in other words if it is information that can be found in almost every authors' writing then that is considered not considered as plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 10). The EUCLID coursepack further, uses the example of the phrase "*smoking causes lung cancer*" it is indeed common understanding (to everyone) that smoking does causes lung cancer. Wherefore, failure to cite the phrase "smoking cause lung cancer" will not amount to plagiarism. The EUCLID unit one coursepack also formulate a basic rule for non-citation of sources by simply stating that "*if it is repeated in many different sources that you have read, then you can assume it is common knowledge*" (ibid.). I also appreciate the fact that the EUCLID course pack (EUCLID 2019, 8) reminds me to have less quotes in my writing especially in both my RP, major papers and thesis. Instead this course encourages the use of paraphrases that are very different from how the author originally wrote it. Furthermore, the course pack generates four (4) important rules when it comes to paraphrasing, namely:

- i) Ensuring that I use my own words as much as possible and ensuring that the I use different language used by the author. This rule encourages originality at all times and guards against merely restructuring the authors words.
- ii) The writing style that I use must be distinct from the writing style of that the author when expressing any authors' ideas.
- iii) The information I am providing must be a true representation of the authors ideas and or opinion.
- iv) Ensure ant after following all the above-mentioned rules, I must still provide a citation indication where my ideas flow from.

3) RULE OF THUMBS FOR WRITING PAPERS

Throughout my writing, I have always written papers that include too much information, little did I know that the best way to produce a good paper is by remaining focus on to the topic that the paper wishes to undress. After reading chapter three (3) of unit one (1) of the EUCLID coursepack. I have learned that the starting point to produce a good thesis is to remain focus on the thesis and the theories that the thesis wishes to undress. Another good principle of writing a good paper is to guard against providing a comprehensive overview of the theory. Instead I should rather guide my presentation by the particular problems animated by my paper (EUCLID 2019, 14). This are good traits to know at this point in time as I am also expected to discuss my thesis with my professor in my next course. I will make sure that my thesis is specific, to the point and that it guards against generalisation! Because this course teaches me that when I generalise my thesis then my thesis could create an impression that I lack enough content to cover, have run out of words and or seem like I'm trying to fill the space.

I am really grateful for this unit and in particular this course (ACA-401D period one), as the course embodies useful skills necessary for both my RP, major paper and thesis writing. Prior to this course, I would write long, unending sentences. I must admit that it was indeed a struggled to produce this RP because I would unintentionally write long sentences, with long paragraphs improperly. I also experienced difficulty finding appropriate connecting words! I Still feel that it is still a very long way for me to apply these rules of thumbs correctly but as the saying goes, I will try my best to do better every time in my response paper and hopefully finish off victorious in my major papers and ultimately in my thesis too. Another rule of thumbs is to avoid boring and clumsy writing (EUCLID 2019, 15) this encourages me to be creative in my writing and to avoid starting my sentences in a similar fashion or with similar words. After reading about the prevailing rule of thumb, I realised that I was about to start my sentence with "I am" and immediately retaliated as I learned that I have to be creative and think out of the box.

There is certain rule of thumbs that I am familiar, such as ensuring to support assertion made in my writing and ensuring that I take views that my paper discusses seriously and avoiding plagiarism at all costs (EUCLID 2019, 16).

4) CONCLUSION

The coursepack under unit one (1) introduced me to very important principles that I should adhere to as a student pursuing studies at Euclid University. Furthermore, it also taught me to choose a more focus thesis and to start my thesis on time in order to conduct an in-depth analysis and research in terms of what other authors wrote on the topic. This skill will ultimately allow me to guard against procrastination. I have also learned about ways to avoid plagiarism such as the use of paraphrasing and the use of in-text citation. Arguably, my course instructor will also notice that I have spent considerable time on chapter four (4) of unit one (1) (ibid.), which discuss the rule of thumbs when it comes to writing. This is so because I realised that I never considered the writing rules of thumbs in

my previous writing prior to registering this course. I am really grateful for this course and more so for chapter four (4) of this unit because learning about the writing rule of thumbs have directed my RP to appear less clumsy.

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